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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Occurrence, formation and fate of micro- and nanoplastics in drinking water treatment and distribution system

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History of edits:		
Version	Date	Ammendments:
v1.0	18/05/21	Initial DMP draft based on DMPonline

AMBITION for DATA MANGEMENT:

The ultimate ambition for this DMP is to maintain a “*living document*” as a research tool, that supports *optimal transparency, reproducibility* and *re-use* of all research outputs by aiming at 100% disclosure by end of project.

Ultimately, this Data Management Plan (v1.0) should evolve into a *Digital Outputs Management Plan*, treating all research outputs of this project as “*data*”, and seeking open file formats, open protocols and pipeline to *make all outputs FAIR and Open*, in full synergy with the MONPLAS Disclosure protocols, and Intellectual Property Right (IPR) exploitation, by referring to MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee & the Dissemination Committee.

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Occurrence, formation and fate of micro- and nanoplastics in drinking water treatment and distribution system - Initial DMP

1. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

- **State the purpose of the data collection/generation**
- **Explain the relation to the objectives of the project**
- **Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected**
- **Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)**
- **Specify the origin of the data**
- **State the expected size of the data (if known)**
- **Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful**

- **Purpose of the data collection/generation**

The project started on the 1st August 2020, so it is to be considered in its initial stage. Research is currently focusing on micro Raman spectroscopy, considered one of the technique capable of addressing the research project theme.

In general, the purpose of data collection is the establishment of a reliable and validated method for assessing micro- and nanoplastics identification and quantification in drinkingwaters. Such a goal will be achieved by means of the combined application of two analytical techniques, the upsaid micro Raman and Pyr- GC/MS.

- **Relation to the objectives of the project**

The project aims to establish suitable analytical methods focusing on the smaller size fraction of microplastics (<10 µm) and nanoplastics (<1 µm). The techniques cited beforeare recognized as very relevant for the purpose of the research, although analytical methodologies for their application in the field are still lacking.

- **Types and formats of data generated/collected**

Legend:

- Written documents
- Real data source
- Instrument-mediated data

Type	PhD Year	Volume	Storage/Dissemination	Expiration	Format	Openness
Literature paper	I	MB	Personal Hardrive Mendeley	N/A	.pdf	Yes
Research diary	I-III	MB	Personal Hardrive	3 years (To be preserved)	.xlsx	Yes
PhD status reports	I-III	MB	Aalborg University Doctoral School repository MONPLAS Box platform	N/A	.txt .pdf	Yes
PhD status presentations	I-III	MB	Aalborg University Doctoral School repository MONPLAS Box platform	N/A	.pptx	Yes
Research papers	II-III	MB	Personal Hardrive Research Group OneDrivecloud Journals repository DOAJ ZENODO LinkedIn Aalborg University VBN	N/A (To be preserved)	.pdf .txt	Yes
Real samples	I-III	-	Laboratory facilities (fridge, freezers,..)	Less than 3 years	-	-
Pictures (of samples, devices, ...)	I-III	MB	Personal Hardrive	N/A (To be preserved)	.jpeg	Yes
Raw spectral data	I-III	GB	Personal Hardrive Instrument PC Research Group OneDrive cloud	N/A (To be preserved)	.wdf .txt .spc	.wdf with limitations (see below)
Processed spectral data	I-III	GB	Personal Hardrive Instrument PC Research Group OneDrive cloud	N/A (To be preserved)	.wdf .txt .spc	.wdf with limitations (see below)

Null spectral data	I-III	GB	Personal Hardrive Instrument PC ZENODO	N/A (To be preserved)	.wdf .txt .spc	.wdf with limitations (see below)
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.wdf extension is automatically produced by the currently employed Raman microscope's software and it is producer-specific.

Periodic reports are produced when requested by the host institution (Aalborg University) and the MONPLAS consortium.

Dissemination and Outreach activities might need the preparation of presentations or audiovisual data, also in lay-man language. During contents presentation, above cited outputs DOIs are cited, in order to assess works credibility and for collaborative purposes.

The following refers to the micro Raman machine currently in use. Specific information about different kind of systems which are going to be employed, will be available in due time.

Raw data are generated from spectral analysis of real samples by means of the instrument (Raman microscopy) and its own software, which encode information in a specific format (.wdf), but also in .spc and .txt. Data elaboration is operated directly on the .wdf files through the machine software, but shareability is possible by converting the related .txt file in .csv. JPEG images are produced during the analytical process as well.

- **Re-using of existing data**

No already existing data are being used at the moment.

- **Origin of data**

Data are originated from the micro Raman analysis of real drinking water samples, after sample preparation has occurred and spectral acquisition is performed. Data post-processing is necessary in order to present findings in significative and understandable way into reports and presentations.

- **Expected size of data**

The expected size of data is GB.

- **Data utility**

Data will be immediately useful for other researchers in the field.

Also, policy makers and drinking waters facilities (treatment companies, aqueducts, public and private laboratories).

Thirdly, bodies and institutions from different research fields (e.g. industrial engineering, management, etc...).

Lastly, the large public during dissemination events and open-access platforms.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for

- **Metadata: Outline the discoverability of data**
(metadata provision)
- **Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?**
- **Outline naming conventions used**
- **Outline the approach towards search keyword**
- **Outline the approach for clear versioning**
- **Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how**

- **Discoverability of data**

Metadata is a priority to be resolved for next version following community standards where they exist.

- **Identifiability of data**

Identifiability and discoverability of data is organized on the basis of DOI numbers.

- **Naming conventions used**

Naming convention for visual images:

YYYY-MM-DD_HOUR_SAMPLE TYPE_MAGNIFICATION
PET_50x

Naming convention for spectral data:

YYYY-MM-DD_HOUR_LASER WAVELENGTH IN
NANOMETERS_MAGNIFICATION_SAMPLE TYPE_ACQUISITION MODE

Example: 2021-05-18_1616_514_50x_PET_single

Example: 2021-05-18_1616_514_50x_PET_map

- **Approach towards search keywords**

N/A

- **Approach for clear versioning**

In the current PhD project, the following definitions for research work entities are employed (Klump, 2021‘Versioning Data Is About More than Revisions: A Conceptual Framework and Proposed Principles’. Data Science Journal 20, no. 1 (23 March 2021):

- **Work:** spectral acquisition (generation of spectral data) from drinking water samples
- **Expression:** a logical data product arising from the Work, in this case microplastics content as number per unit volume and chemical nature
- **Manifestation:** specific structure of files. Any kind of modification of this structure is considered a new Manifestation
- **Item:** a certain data file in a repository

The following schematic shows the relations among these entities.

Legend:

→ “Leads to”

• **Metadata creation**

Metadata are represented by DOI numbers, which are also collected under ORCID account.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

- **Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so**
- **Specify how the data will be made available**

- **Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- **Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited**
- **Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions**

- **Openly available data**

Null data and final peer-reviewed data will be openly available for opposite reasons: the former to offer an overview of wrong approaches, the latter to show a correct workflow. In both cases the aim is to allow an effective improvement of the field state-of-art.

Raw and processed data will be kept closed to guarantee the necessary intellectual property and to consent scientific reflection around them.

- **Availability of data**

Null data will be shared on LinkedIn and ZENODO, while final peer-reviewed data through scientific journals too.

- **Methods and software tools for accessing data**

PC, internet connection.

- **Data and metadata repository**

Peer-reviewed data and metadata are always associated as unique file. See above for the chosen open-access platforms.

- **Access in case of any restrictions**

N/A

2.3 Making data interoperable:

- **Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.**

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in

- **your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?**

Interoperability of data

MONPLAS is engaging the Spectroscopy community to seek operational standards for metadata and standard vocabularies to facilitate inter-disciplinary interoperability. This will be a priority for next version update

- **Inter-disciplinary interoperability**

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Standard vocabularies will be used to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- **Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible**
- **Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed**
- **Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why**
- **Describe data quality assurance processes**
- **Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable**

- **Data licence**

CC-BY is chosen as form of data licence.

- **Re-use of data**

A data embargo of 3 years is indicated for data re-use.

- **Third party use of data**

As in the previous point, in order to avoid conflicts during the research development.

- **Data quality assurance processes**

Peer-review.

- **Length of time for data re-use**

N/A

3. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- - **Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs**
 - **Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project**
Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

- **Open access costs coverage**

N/A

- **Data management responsible**

- N/A

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- **Costs and potential value of long term preservation**

About 6000 EUR for three peer-reviewed publications during the fellowship. Long-term preservation value to be evaluated at a later stage.

4. Data security

Data will be duplicated in physical harddrives as well as in the host institution cloud in order to ensure secure storage. Files security in the latter option is up to those host institution's IT Department. In addition, mature datasets with a DOI will be permanently stored in ZENODO.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

The project does not expect experimentation on living animals, human beings, cells or their parts.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for datamanagement that you are using (if any)

The present document must not be considered definitive in any of its part and is subjected to constant update.

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